

Assessing radiative properties of extreme pollen events observed by synergy remote sensors in South-Eastern Iberian Peninsula

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1. Introduction

The study of bioaerosols in the atmosphere has been gaining raising interest during the last years. Airborne pollen particles have important effects on climate, air quality, human health and biodiversity. The population affected by allergies due to pollen inhalation is rising and pollen injected in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is considered as an air pollutant affecting incoming solar radiation and cloud properties by acting as both condensation and ice nuclei.

These effects will alter in the context of the current climate change, since the timing of the main pollen season and pollen concentrations are expected to change (Beggs, 2021; Ziska, 2020). Allergic diseases such as allergic rhinitis and allergic asthma, among others, might be changing (D'Amato et al., 2020; Eguluz-Gracia et al., 2020) and climate change might induce an asynchrony between pollen and pollinators life cycles due to temperature and other environmental shifts, leading to a subsequent reduction in populations (Nicholson and Egan, 2020; Soroye et al., 2020). Thus, further research is needed to better understand the biological basis for these effects, the meteorological factors involved and their consequences on climate and atmospheric physics.

In previous studies, a link between daily pollen concentrations and surface temperature, global solar radiation, relative humidity, air pressure, and wind speed was reported during extreme pollen events (EPEs) (Csépe et al., 2012), being surface temperature one of the most influential variables both on the day on which the EPE is registered and in the previous days, together with ambient relative humidity (Cariñanos et al., 2022). However, studies on the vertical distribution of pollen properties and the influence of vertical distribution of meteorological variables are scarce, with only a few studies reported in the literature. Raynor et al. (1975) studied the vertical distribution of pollen emissions using a 108-m tower and found that it was partly correlated with variability in meteorological conditions. Comtois et al. (2000) used a tethered balloon up to 600 m and biased to the first hours of the morning, reporting different airborne pollen types, and identifying the mixing ratio, air temperature and wind speed as meteorological variables governing pollen concentrations at different altitudes. Nevertheless, these data were very limited in time and vertical extension. The use of remote sensors such as lidars or ceilometers and sun-photometers allows for a much more extended analysis, from the surface up to several kilometres and with (or almost-) continuous measurements or detailed analysis of daily patterns. Noh et al. (2013) analysed diurnal patterns of the vertical distribution of pollen grains by lidar measurements and Sicard et al. (2016) presented a detailed analysis of pollen vertical properties during an specific event using an MPL system.

In this work, we investigate a historical database covering almost 10 years of data (2013-2021, both included) to perform an aerosol characterization of the vertical profiles of optical, microphysical and radiative properties of extreme pollen events (EPEs) observed also by near surface aerobiological techniques over Granada, Spain. These EPEs were synergically analysed by remote sensors (ceilometer plus Sun-photometer) applying the GRASPPac (Román et al., 2018) code to the historic

dataset. The aerosol properties were used as input to the radiative transfer models GAME (Global Atmospheric Model) and lidRadtran (library for radiative transfer) to investigate the differences in the estimations from both codes, making a special emphasis in the analysis of the longwave component. Since pollen particles are quite large, a significant contribution is expected, even though the longwave component analysis of the radiative properties is still affected by large uncertainties due to the lack of experimental data. After the comparative analysis, the libRadtran model was used for the analysis of radiative properties for the complete period in order to further investigate pollen radiative impact.

2. Methodology and dataset

In this work, extreme pollen events (EPEs) observed by near surface aerobiological techniques over Granada, Spain, were analysed with remote sensors from the AGORA-UGR station. Specifically, measurements from the ceilometer CHM15K Nimbus, operated within ICENET (Cazorla et al., 2017) (and E-PROFILE), and the Sun-Photometer CIMEL CE318 from AERONET (Holben et al., 1998) were used to retrieve the aerosol optical and microphysical properties of pollen particles using the GRASPPac software through the CAECENET system (Román et al., 2018). The database is complemented by pollen surface measurements with a Hirst Lanzoni VPPS 2000 volumetric sampler.

2.1. Experimental site and instrumentation

The instrumentation used in this study is part of the main station (UGR) of the AGORA observatory. This UGR station is located in the Andalusian Institute for Earth System Research (IISTA-CEAMA), in Granada (37.16°N, 3.61°W, 680 m a.s.l.), and managed by the Atmospheric Physics Group (GFAT) of the University of Granada. Granada is located at 200 km from the African continent and at 50 km from the Mediterranean Sea, being characterized for the presence of long-range transported mineral dust particles (Lyamani et al., 2005; Valenzuela et al., 2012). Dust intrusions mostly happen during the summer season (Bravo-Aranda et al., 2015; Granados-Muñoz et al., 2016), but extreme winter dust events have occurred more frequently in the past few years (Cazorla et al., 2017; Fernández et al., 2019). The region is often affected by episodes of aerosol stagnation due to its complex geography (e.g. Lyamani et al., 2010), while Atlantic air masses are usually responsible for cleaning the atmosphere (Pérez-Ramírez et al., 2016). A large presence of anthropogenic aerosols is also observed, mainly in winter (e.g. Casquero-Vera et al., 2021; del Águila et al., 2018; Lyamani et al., 2010) and primary aerosols associated with the local phenology (Cariñanos et al., 2020). EPEs events are usually observed at the surface level with a predominant presence of Cupressaceae and *Olea* taxa (Cariñanos et al., 2022), but their vertical distribution has not been studied until now.

The CE318 (Cimel Electronique) sun-sky photometer, which is part of the AEROSOL RObotic NETwork (AERONET) since 2004, routinely measuring at the AGORA/Granada station, is used for the analysis presented here. This multi-wavelength sun-sky photometer performs measurements of the direct solar irradiance, used to derive the aerosol optical depth (AOD), and sky radiance at several wavelengths (440, 675, 870 and 1020 nm). The photometer raw data from Granada, together with the rest of the stations in Spain, are sent to CAELIS (Fuertes et al., 2018), a system operated by the Atmospheric Optics Group of the University of Valladolid (GOA-UVa). These data are filtered and pre-processed by CAELIS (González et al., 2020) and, if successful, submitted and processed by AERONET (Dubovik et al., 2006; Dubovik and King, 2000; Sinyuk et al., 2007).

The IISTA-CEAMA station is also equipped with a Lufft CHM15k-Nimbus ceilometer, which belongs to the Iberian CEilometer NETwork (ICENET; Cazorla et al., 2017), a network of ceilometers in the Iberian Peninsula. This ceilometer operates with a pulsed laser that emits at 1064 nm and collects the backscattered signal on a telescope. Each pulse has an energy of 8.4 μ J, with a frequency between 5 and 7 kHz. The ceilometer has a vertical resolution of 15 m, and is overlap corrected providing reliable data from 240 m a.g.l. The Range Corrected Signal (RCS) at 1064 nm is collected continuously every 15 seconds from the surface up to 15 km. Data from the ICENET network are

daily processed using the GRASPPac inversion method (Román et al., 2018) that combines information from the ceilometer RCS with the AOD and sky radiance from the sun-sky photometer to retrieve optical and microphysical aerosol properties. More details about GRASPPac are provided in Section 2.2.

At the surface level, airborne pollen grains are regularly collected by a Hirst-type volumetric spore trap (HIRST, 1952). This sampler actively collects airborne pollen grains by sucking a constant flow of air of 10 l/min, uninterrupted 24 h per day, 365 days per year. The qualitative analysis by optical microscopy of the samples allows for identifying different pollen taxa, leading to quantitatively determining daily pollen concentrations (Galán et al., 2007). The sampler in Granada is placed at the roof of the Faculty of Sciences (37.181°N, 3.609°W) about 20 m above surface, in the city center, an area of intense traffic, dense urbanization, and with high presence of pollen sources emission in its vicinity.

2.2. The GRASPPac algorithm

The GRASPPac (subscript “pac” from photometer and ceilometer) inversion method, described in Román et al. (2018), was developed following the GARRLiC scheme (Generalized Aerosol Retrieval from Radiometer and Lidar Combined data) algorithm, described in Lopatin et al. (2013). GARRLiC is a part of the GRASP algorithm developed by (Dubovik et al., 2014). The GRASPPac combines coincident ceilometer measurements (RCS at 1064 nm) and sun-sky photometer measurements (direct sun irradiance and sky radiance at 440, 675, 870 and 1020 nm), performing an inversion of these measurements under cloud-free conditions. This method has been used successfully implemented (Herrerias et al., 2019; Titos et al., 2019) and is currently implemented in CAECENET (Román et al., 2022). CAECENET is a combination of CAELIS and ICENET that automatically assimilates sun-photometer data (AOD and sky radiances) at almucantar and AERONET hybrid scenarios (Antuña-Sánchez et al., 2021; Román et al., 2022; Sinyuk et al., 2020) from CAELIS (González et al., 2020) and ceilometer data (RCS at 1064 nm) from ICENET and run GRASP in near-real-time using both datasets under the GRASPPac method (Román et al., 2018). CAECENET provides the retrieved aerosol optical and microphysical properties in all the stations with data in both ICENET and AERONET networks, such as UGR station. The columnar and vertical aerosol properties retrieved by GRASPPac, such as extinction, aerosol optical depth (AOD), asymmetry factor (ASY), single scattering and albedo (SSA) among others, have been directly obtained from CAECENET in this work.

2.3. The radiative transfer models: GAME and libRadtran

The aerosol properties retrieved by CAECENET are used as input to the radiative transfer models GAME (Global Atmospheric Model; Dubuisson et al., 2004) and libRadtran (Emde et al., 2016; Mayer and Kylling, 2005) to further investigate pollen radiative impact. A special emphasis is put in the analysis of the longwave (LW) component since pollen particles are quite large and a significant contribution is expected (Granados-Muñoz et al., 2019).

The GAME code, described in Dubuisson et al. (2005, 2004, 1996) and Sicard et al. (2014), is a RTM that calculates transmittances over a spectral interval with the use of the correlated k distribution approximation. The model uses the discrete ordinates method (Stamnes et al., 1988) to account for scattering processes and interactions between absorption and scattering, solving the radiative transfer equation at each wavelength assuming a plane-parallel atmosphere. Since the model requires atmospheric parameters at each atmospheric layer, it allows for obtaining vertical profiles of radiative fluxes. GAME has proven to be a powerful tool for calculating radiative fluxes at different vertical levels (Bazo et al., 2023; Granados-Muñoz et al., 2019; Sicard et al., 2014). It works at two different adjustable spectral ranges, which for this study have been established as 0.297-3.1 μm for the SW range (Bazo et al., 2023; Granados-Muñoz et al., 2019) and 4.5-100 μm for the LW one. In both ranges, we have set 80 vertical levels, covering heights from the surface up to 20 km above it, with

decreasing resolution (0.1 km from 0 to 6 km, 0.25 km from 6 km to 6.5 km, 0.5 km from 6.5 km to 10 km, and 1 km from 10 km to 20 km). Daily radiative fluxes have been calculated following the same methodology as Di Biagio et al. (2014) and Bazo et al. (2023) that establishes the solar zenith angle at 60°.

The libRadtran (Emde et al., 2016; Mayer and Kylling, 2005) is a software package, which main tool is the uvspec program that allows for radiative transfer calculations for a variety of atmospheric conditions. In the calculations performed with libRadtran, the gas absorption parameterization lowtran (code adopted from SBDART; Ricchiazzi et al., 1998) was considered and the discrete-ordinate method disort (Buras et al., 2011) was used to solve the radiative transfer equation for a plane parallel atmosphere approximation. The model requires the atmospheric parameters at different layers to calculate the vertical profiles of the radiative fluxes. The calculations were performed for the same vertical levels as used in GAME.

The calculation of the radiative fluxes by the radiative transfer models (RTMs) requires several input variables, such as meteorological profiles, surface properties and an aerosol model. The aerosol model is established by the spectral AOD, SSA and ASY. In both spectral ranges we have considered standard atmosphere profiles (Anderson et al., 1986; Krueger and Minzner, 1976) of middle-latitudes for the meteorological conditions. In libRadtran calculations, the water vapour and the total ozone column values from ERA reanalysis (downloaded from <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu>; last access on 13 June 2023) were also considered. The surface albedo in the SW range was selected from MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) (Ichoku et al., 2004; Remer et al., 2005) MCD43C3 Version 6 Albedo Model dataset (Wang et al., 2015), which provides radiances at seven wavelengths from 0.670 to 2.155 μm . For libRadtran calculations, the surface albedo in the SW was retrieved from the AERONET for the wavelengths 440, 675, 870 and 1020 nm and in the extremes of the spectral range, the approximation by Abreu et al. (2020) was considered. In the LW range, the surface albedo and the surface temperature were obtained from CERES (Cloud and the Earth's Radiant System) (Wielicki et al., 1998), database SSF Level 2 and used in simulations by both RTMs. In the SW range, aerosol properties that constitute the aerosol model in both RTMs have been obtained from CAECENET by the mentioned GRASPPac method. However, these properties are not available in the LW range, so it is necessary to apply a Mie code, included as a module in GAME. The aerosol number concentration, the geometric median radius and the standard deviation for fine and coarse modes are obtained from the size distribution retrieved by GRASPPac. These variables, along with the refractive index in the infrared range, are the input variables in the Mie code. As an output, the AOD, SSA and ASY in the LW are obtained and used for the retrieval of the aerosol radiative effects. For libRadtran, the methodology proposed in Molero et al. (2020) was adapted to construct the aerosol layer properties, which requires the wavelength, extinction coefficients, SSA, ASY and moments of the phase function. In this case, the LW extinction coefficients are calculated using the Ångström exponent obtained from the CAECENET AOD.

2.4. Data analysis

As a first step for the data analysis, it is necessary to obtain the EPEs database for the complete period 2013-2021. For the selection of EPEs, a threshold on the 24-h accumulated pollen concentrations from the Hirst measurements was considered. Specifically, pollen concentrations over the 95th percentile calculated for a quasi-climatological data series collected at Granada were identified as EPEs, as indicated in Cariñanos et al. (2022). The surface measurements were used as a first filter for the identification of the EPEs. However, in order to guarantee the presence of pollen particles in the atmospheric column and not only at the surface, it was necessary to implement a routinary filter to exclude mineral dust cases. Mineral dust particles may have similar microphysical and optical properties to those of pollen and needs to be excluded to avoid the contamination of the results. For this, we used a back-trajectories analysis. The 5-day backtrajectories were retrieved each 500 m between 500 and 3000 m asl with HYSPLIT for each of the analysed days affected by EPEs and those that were overflying the Sahara region were excluded from the analysis. In addition, a detailed

inspection of ceilometer and sun-photometer data to confirm the presence of pollen above the surface was performed to guarantee the quality of the database. Once the database was established, the aerosol properties retrieved with GRASPPac were used as input to the radiative transfer models GAME and libRadtran to further investigate pollen radiative impact. The differences between the two RTMs were analysed in detail for two case studies. The comparative analysis revealed some discrepancies between both codes, even though not significant due to the large uncertainty a variability of the radiative properties themselves. Due to technical difficulties and the fact that the GAME code available is technically obsolete and not open-access, it was decided to use libRadtran for a more comprehensive pollen radiative impact analysis using the complete database.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Characterization of the aerosol optical and microphysical properties

A detailed classification of EPEs was performed using surface measurements from the Hirst collector, as explained in the previous section. The pollen concentration for both *Olea* and Cupressaceae during the EPEs for the complete period is presented in Figure 1. In general, more Cupressaceae EPEs are observed over Granada region (172 cases) and early in the year, during winter-early spring months, whereas *Olea* EPEs occur later in the year (late-spring and summer) and are less frequent (95 cases). In general, concentration values are larger for the *Olea* taxa, with an average concentration of 1377 ± 579 grains \cdot m $^{-3}$ \cdot day $^{-1}$, compared to the Cupressaceae ones, with an average of 1178 ± 887 grains \cdot m $^{-3}$ \cdot day $^{-1}$, even though the Cupressaceae presents larger variability. The Cupressaceae number concentration has reached extreme values during the 2020 and 2021, with concentrations over 3000 grains \cdot m $^{-3}$ \cdot day $^{-1}$.

Figure 1. Pollen concentration time series during EPEs observed by the Hirst collector at Granada during 2013-2021.

The analysis of the surface measurements was completed with remote sensing measurements that allowed the characterization of pollen column-integrated and vertically resolved properties for the different pollen taxa plumes. Data from the sun-photometer and the ceilometer were analyzed with the GRASPPac code, as indicated in the methodology. Because of the lower availability of sun-photometer data compared to the surface and ceilometer measurements, the number of available data was reduced and a total of 44 days for *Olea* and 59 for Cupressaceae taxa were analyzed. The average extinction profiles at 1064 nm and column-integrated particle size distribution for each pollen type are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Averaged extinction profiles at 1064 nm (top) and particle size distribution (bottom) for Cupressaceae (left), *Olea* (center) and the comparison of both taxa (right) during EPEs in the period 2013-2021.

According to the extinction profiles, the pollen particles might be confined between the surface and up to 3500 m a.s.l, where the concentrations tend to zero. The Cupressaceae pollen taxa are more abundant closer to the surface, whereas above 1750 m a.s.l. the *Olea* taxa presents larger concentration. This difference is associated to the fact that *Olea* events appear later in the year, in late spring and summer, where the convective activity within the mixing layer is higher due to the larger surface temperatures and the pollen particles can reach higher altitudes. However, values are quite similar and, considering their large variability, these differences are not significant. As already observed at the surface level, the Cupressaceae data present much more variability than the *Olea* data. The column-integrated particle size distribution reveals that the atmospheric events including *Olea* grains are associated to larger particles than the Cupressaceae data, with an average effective radius of $0.58 \pm 0.22 \mu\text{m}$ versus $0.38 \pm 0.13 \mu\text{m}$. According to Figure 3, not significant differences are observed in the averaged AOD values. The SSA presents slightly larger values for the events including Cupressaceae taxa in the shorter wavelengths, whereas the cases including *Olea* taxa seems to be more scattering in the wavelengths above 660 nm. The real refractive index values are slightly larger for the events including *Olea* taxa, whereas according to the imaginary refractive index the events including Cupressaceae taxa are more absorbing. These small discrepancies will affect the radiative properties during the events of both taxa, even though the large variability and the associated uncertainties imply that the observed differences are not significant.

Figure 3. Averaged AOD (top left), SSA (bottom left), real refractive index (top right) and imaginary refractive index values (bottom right) for columns including Cupressaceae (orange) and *Olea* (green) during EPEs in the period 2013-2021.

3.2 Evaluation of the estimations of radiative properties provided by GAME and libRadtran

A comparative analysis of the radiative properties retrieved with GAME and libRadtran was performed for two EPEs, i.e., an *Olea* event on 18 May 2017, and a Cupressaceae event on 22 February 2019. From the Hirt collector, similar surface concentration on both days are observed (1727 and 1780 grains \cdot m $^{-3}$ \cdot day $^{-1}$ for *Olea* and Cupressaceae, respectively). Figure 4 shows an overview of the two events. The RCS at 1064 nm from the ceilometer shows that the aerosol particles reach up to 2.5 km a.s.l. on both cases, with higher concentration values closer to the surface. The particle size distribution shows a predominance of coarse particles, even though the *Olea* case presents larger values of the radii.

The aerosol extinction profiles at 1064 nm and the corresponding total aerosol radiative effects (ARE) profiles, including the SW and LW component, obtained with both GAME and libRadtran are shown in Figure 5. According to the extinction profiles, aerosol particles are observed up to 2.5 km a.s.l. for both cases, with larger extinction values for the Cupressaceae event compared to the *Olea* case. In the *Olea* event, two different layers are distinguished in the early morning, but the mixed along the day showing quite homogeneous profiles. For the Cupressaceae event, most of the aerosol is located below 2 km a.s.l. before 15:30 h, but a more homogeneous layer is observed during the afternoon. Regarding the ARE, larger absolute values are obtained for the Cupressaceae case, as expected, since it is highly dependent on the aerosol load. From the figure, it is clear that there are some discrepancies between both RTMs, GAME and libRadtran, being larger in the Cupressaceae event. Even though the shape of the ARE profiles correlates quite well, an offset between both models is observed.

Figure 4. (Left) Ceilometer RCS at 1064 nm and CAECENET provided AOD time series for the *Olea* (top) and Cupressaceae (bottom) events. Vertical color lines indicate the periods when optical and radiative properties are retrieved. (Right) GRASPac retrieved particle size distributions at different UTC times for the same events.

Figure 5. GRASPac retrieved aerosol extinction profiles at 1064 nm (color solid lines) and total ARE (SW+LW) profiles retrieved using GAME (grey dashed lines) and libRadtran (blue dotted lines). The top row corresponds to the *Olea* event and the bottom row represents the Cupressaceae event.

Table 1 presents the ARE values at the surface obtained with both models and separated in SW and LW component. The ratio between the LW and SW component is also presented, together with the AOD values at 440 nm for each of the analyzed profiles. In Figure 6, we present the average difference between the GAME and libRadtran retrieved ARE profiles and their standard deviation, also distinguishing between the different spectral components. As observed, differences are much larger in general for the Cupressaceae case. The difference is especially relevant in the LW component, with values around $3.8 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, which are larger than the values obtained for the ARE itself (see Table 1). For the SW component, differences oscillate around $4 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, which is quite reasonable compared to the ARE values obtained and considering the large uncertainties still affecting

the retrieval of radiative properties with RTMs, but still non-negligible. For the *Olea* event, differences come close to $0 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ in the LW spectral range and below $2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ for the SW component, which are not significant considering the uncertainty associated to the retrieval with RTMs.

Both models, GAME and libRadtran, has proven to be robust and reliable in previous studies (i.e., Bazo et al., 2023; Molero et al., 2021) and, despite the differences, results obtained are similar to those retrieved in previous studies for large aerosol particles (e.g. mineral dust, see Granados-Muñoz et al., 2019; Sicard et al., 2014). Comparison with previous results for pollen particles is not possible due to their scarce availability in the literature, so this study is a first step to improve the retrieval of pollen radiative properties, even though more research on this topic is necessary. The analysis of pollen properties, either optical, microphysical or radiative in the vertical coordinate using remote sensors is still in its early stages and more dedicated studies are needed in order to improve our understanding.

Figure 6. Mean differences (and their standard deviation as error bars) between the ARE profiles retrieved with GAME and libRadtran for the total (left), SW (middle) and LW components (right). Green lines correspond to the *Olea* event and orange lines to the Cupressaceae event.

Table 1. AOD (440 nm) and the corresponding ARE at the surface for SW and LW spectral ranges and their ratio for both EPEs (top: *Olea*, bottom: Cupressaceae). Times are UTC. LRT stands for libRadtran.

<i>Olea</i>	06:28		07:57		15:24		16:19		17:32		18:02	
AOD (440 nm)	0.08		0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04		0.03	
ARE _{SW} (GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	-15.5	-10.2	-9.6	-9.4	-6	-6	-6.5	-3.9	-7.6	-7.4	-6.6	-6.6
ARE _{LW} (GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	1.7	0.3	1.8	0.1	1.4	0.5	1.7	0.6	0.9	1.2	0.7	1
LW/SW(GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	11	3	19	1	23	9	26	15	12	17	10	15
<i>Cupressaceae</i>	12:30		13:30		14:30		15:30		16:12		16:42	
AOD (440 nm)	0.18		0.16		0.16		0.18		0.18		0.17	
ARE _{SW} (GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	-13.6	-13.9	-12.5	-10.5	-13.1	-10	-19.6	-12.9	-22	-19.9	-21.2	-13.3
ARE _{LW} (GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	4.1	6	2.4	4.1	2.4	2.2	2.6	2.1	2.8	3.8	2.7	4.3
LW/SW(GAME/LRT) [Wm ⁻²]	30	43	19	39	18	22	13	16	12	19	13	32

3.3 Long-term characterization of the aerosol radiative properties

A long-term analysis of the radiative properties associated to EPEs is presented in this section. Long-term analysis of ARE are scarce in the literature (Bazo et al., 2023) and even more rare in the case of bioaerosol particles. In this study, we retrieved the ARE daily profiles during EPEs of *Olea* and Cupressaceae pollen events for the complete period 2013-2021 using libRadtran, fed with the optical and microphysical properties retrieved with the GRASPPac algorithm. libRadtran is an open-access code in continuous development, whereas GAME is not freely available and some of their technical components are obsolete, making it very time consuming. Considering that both provide reliable and robust results according to the literature and our previous section, libRadtran has been preferred over GAME for the long-term analysis in this study.

Figure 7 shows ARE mean vertical profiles for the SW and LW components and total ARE (SW+LW) for 2013-2021 period obtained from libRadtran for a solar zenith angle of 60° . In the SW spectral range, the Cupressaceae presents low absolute values at low altitudes (approximately up to 1.7 km) in comparison with *Olea*. This situation inverts approximately above 1.7 km and this can be explained by the vertical distribution of the Cupressaceae and *Olea* concentrations (most of the Cupressaceae pollen are closer to the surface while *Olea* taxa presents larger concentrations above 1.7 km). Because of the vertical distribution of Cupressaceae and the aerosol properties (described section 3.1), it was expected a larger contribution of Cupressaceae close to the surface. In table 2, the mean ARE SW contribution per year at the surface shows larger absolute values for Cupressaceae in comparison with *Olea* in the same years. The LW component of ARE (Figure 7) shows similar behaviour between Cupressaceae and *Olea* for 2013-2021, but with larger values for Cupressaceae in all profile. In this case, it was expected a larger contribution by *Olea* since its grains are associated to larger particles. However, Figure 7 shows the mean values of all available profiles (2013-2021), but in table 2, the mean values per year show that in general *Olea* presents slightly high values in the LW at the surface. The profile of the total ARE (Figure 7) due to the EPEs are mainly controlled by the SW component.

Figure 7. Mean vertical profiles of ARE (2013-2021) for SW and LW spectral ranges and total (SW+LW) retrieved from libRadtran calculations for *Olea* and Cupressaceae EPEs. The profiles correspond to a solar zenith angle of 60° .

Table 2. ARE mean values at the surface for SW, LW and Total (Wm^{-2}) obtained from libRadtran calculations for a solar zenith angle of 60° for the different *Olea* and Cupressaceae EPEs.

		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2013-2021
<i>Olea</i>	SW	-26.5	-38.4	-13.2	-13.9	-11.7	-12.4	-8.4	-	-7.3	-14.1
	LW	0.3	0.4	1.2	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.3	-	0.2	0.4
<i>Cupre.</i>	SW	-	-50.2	-	-19.5	-15.6	-13.2	-9.7	-9.6	-9.7	-13.5
	LW	-	2.4	-	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.7	0.2	0.2	0.5

4. Concluding remarks

For the first time, a long-term analysis of EPEs for *Olea* and Cupressaceae taxa covering the period 2013-2021 in the city of Granada, Spain, using remote sensors combined with surface measurements is presented here. The use of remote sensors allows for the detailed analysis of the pollen properties in the vertical coordinate.

The analysis of the optical and microphysical properties, retrieved with the GRASPPac software using CAECENET, reveals that pollen particles are predominantly large and non-absorbing particles that can reach up to 3 km a.s.l. in large concentrations. The optical and microphysical properties retrieved with GRASPPac can be used as input in RTMs to estimate their radiative impact. A comparison between the two RTMs, GAME and libRadtran, reveals that their radiative impact is not negligible either in the shortwave or longwave components, even though some discrepancies are found between both models.

The long term analysis shows similar ARE between Cupressaceae and *Olea*, varying in altitude according with the vertical distribution of the pollen grains. The ARE mean values at the surface per year shows a slight larger contribution of Cupressaceae for the SW component and a slight larger contribution *Olea* for the LW component. The aerosol radiative effects due to the EPEs in SW and LW spectral ranges need further analysis, mainly in the LW spectral range where the aerosol properties are not completely known.

The methodology implemented here allows for an automatic characterization of pollen optical, microphysical and radiative properties along the vertical coordinate. However, the analysis of the radiative properties is still affected by large uncertainties since scarce information about the bioaerosol particles is available, especially in the LW spectral range. Further investigation on pollen optical properties is crucial since databases are still scarce.

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